

Table I. Characterisation of the study samples.

Variable	Sample distribution
Coordinating region: organising region and number of projects or initiatives.	<u>Western Europe</u>
	Austria (9)
	Belgium (14)
	France (18)
	Germany (15)
	Switzerland (5)
	The Netherlands (14)
	<u>Northern Europe</u>
	Denmark (3)
	Estonia (2)
	Finland (2)
	Ireland (9)
	Lithuania (1)
	Norway (7)
	Sweden (2)
	UK (26)
	<u>Eastern Europe</u>
	Bulgaria (8)
	Czech Republic (1)
	Hungary (6)
	Poland (6)
	Romania (4)
	Slovakia (1)
	<u>Southern Europe</u>
	Croatia (1)
	Greece (3)
	Italy (15)
	Portugal (8)
	Slovenia (3)
	Spain (17)
Domain: field to which the project/initiative belongs.	Agriculture (156)
	Agro-Food (1)
	Forestry (12)
	Rural development (31)
Innovation type: the innovation type of the project/initiative	Marketing innovation (6)
	Organisational innovation (15)
	Process innovation (94)
	Product innovation (37)
	Social innovation (27)

Variable	Sample distribution
	Others (21)
Gender balance: equality of the project/initiative participants in relation to their gender	Gender Equality (100) More men than women (65) More women than men (35)
Geographic magnitude: the project/initiative's geographic scope	District-based (1) Local (20) Multinational (79) National (47) Regional (53)

Table II. Categories and issue factors identified with the state-of-the-art analysis

Category	Issue factor	Code	Bibliographic reference
Social	Level of public opposition to the project	RF1	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Lack of organisation and coordination	RF2	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Inadequate experience in PPP (Public Private Partnership)	RF3	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Distribution of responsibilities and risks	RF4	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Unsuitably distributed authority	RF5	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Differences in partners' work methods and knowledge	RF6	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Lack of partner commitment	RF7	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Breaching the project's terms	RF8	(Zou <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
	Social or cultural problems	RF9	(Söderholm, 2008)
	Lack of communication	RF10	(Esteves <i>et al.</i> , 2017)

Category	Issue factor	Code	Bibliographic reference
	Unfavourable relationships with the other actors	RF11	Created by the authors
	Identification of actors	RF12	Created by the authors
Economic	No available economic funds	RF13	(Santalova <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
	Project's financial appeal to investors	RF14	(Boateng <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
	High financial costs	RF15	(Bruzelius <i>et al.</i> , 2002)
Environmental	Force majeure	RF16	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Geotechnical conditions	RF17	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Climate	RF18	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Natural environment	RF19	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
Political	Unstable government	RF20	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Bad public decision-making process	RF21	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Political opposition/hostility	RF22	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Excessive administrative regulations/management	RF23	Created by the authors
Technical	Technical problems	RF24	(Nielsen and Randall, 2013)
	Mistakes in planning the project	RF25	(Santalova <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
	Unexpected modification to the project	RF26	(Ghosh and Jintanapakanont, 2004)
Legal	Change in legislation	RF27	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
	Change in tax laws	RF28	(Bing <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
Innovation	Negative R&D outcomes	RF29	(Santalova <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

Category	Issue factor	Code	Bibliographic reference
Other	Does not match any of the defined options	RF30	Created by the authors

*Approach by means of which the risk factor was dealt with in research.

Table III. Frequency of risk factors per category.

Risk category	Related risk factors	Percentage (%)
Social	108	54
Economic	20	10
Environmental	2	1
Political	20	10
Technical	27	14
Legal	6	3
Innovation	0	0
Other	8	4
None	9	5